

Intellectual Traditions in Ancient Greek (and Latin) texts: A Co-occurrence Network Approach

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NIKAW NETWORKS OF IDEAS AND KNOWLEDGE IN THE ANCIENT WORLD

What?

Using the mentions of people in Ancient Greek and Latin texts to understand the dynamics of knowledge circulation in the Greek and Roman world (7th century BCE- 4th century CE)

How?

- Natural Language Processing
- Social Network Analysis

When?

2023-2027

OUR GOAL

- Automatically create networks based on co-occurrence in Greek and Latin literature to study co-occurrence of individuals in text

PRE-PROCESSING PAULYS REALENCYCLOPÄDIE

(COLLABORATION WITH THE TRISMEGISTOS+ TEAM)

- Local copy based on Register (98,577 articles)
 - Categorized based on keywords
 - Manual check
- 48,749 entries identified as Persons
 - Complete name restored & split into constituent elements (e.g. Caius Iulius Caesar = “Caius”, “Iulius”, “Caesar”)
 - Linked to TM name variant (TM NamVar), name (TM Nam) and author (TM Author)
 - Pageweight based on the *Seite* (pages)

A search tool facilitating access to the *RE* based on this work is now available at <https://www.trismegistos.org/real>

CASE STUDY: TEXTS WITH MENTIONS OF PLATO

Prolific author with well documented influence on both Christian and Non-Christian authors

Proof of concept NIKAW

- Clear picture of strengths and limitations of approach

Gold annotated NEL data

- Further evaluation of coverage selected Knowledge Base (KB): Paulys Realencyclopädie der classischen Altertumswissenschaft (RE)
- Can be used for training models

Network model

- Clear definition of Nodes, Edges, and Attributes
- Clear definition of network properties and appropriate analytics

SELECTED TEXTS: BASE CRITERIA

Lemma “Platon”/
“Πλάτων” > 5 times

Between 800 BCE
and 450 CE

Varying text types

Varying intellectual
backgrounds

Author	Work	Period	Christian work
Greek [GLAUx corpus]			
[Plato]	Epistulae	BCE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Aristoteles	Metaphysica	BCE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Strabo	Geographica	BCE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dionysius Halicarnassensis	De Demosthenis dictione	BCE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plutarchus	Quaestiones convivales	CE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Claudius Aelianus	Varia historia	CE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Clemens Alexandrinus	Stromata	CE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Origenes	Contra Celsum	CE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Diogenes Laertius	Vitae philosophorum	CE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Galenus	De placitis Hippocratis et Platonis	CE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Latin [LASLA / Corpus Latin]			
Cicero	Tusculanae Disputationes	BCE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tertullian	De Anima	CE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Seneca	Ad Lucilium Epistulae Morales	CE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lactantius	Divinarum Institutionum	CE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Apuleius	Pro Se De Magia Liber	CE	<input type="checkbox"/>

Social Network Analysis

MULTI-MODAL GRAPH SCHEMA

Attributes

- ID
- Complete name
- Dates
- Gender
- Author
- School of Thought
- Pageweight
- Total occurrences

Attributes

- ID
- Date
- Language
- Genre

Attributes

- ID
- Reference

CO-OCCURRENCE NETWORKS: INSPIRATION

Character constellations

Literary Characters

- Proximity
- Interaction

Bibliometrics

Authors in scholarly articles

- Proximity
- Similarity

Author co-mention analysis

Authors mentioned in reviews

- Proximity

Archeology

Material culture

- Similarity

Methodological question:
Can proximity be used to
approximate similarity between
individuals recorded in our
corpus? (Cf. Grayson et al.
2016; Smeets 2021)

For full bibliography on these topics, see the [abstract on Zenodo](#)

CO-OCCURRENCE PROJECTIONS

Co-occurrence (A,B) exists if person A co-occurs with person B within pre-defined sub-section (div_1, smallest div and sliding window of two sentences)

Weighted

The aggregated weight for two entities

$$w(A, B) = \frac{N}{\sum(\frac{1}{d_i})}$$

where:

- N = number of distance measurements (total co-occurring mention pairs)
- d_i = distance between individual mentions of A and B

First experiments: Greek corpus

NETWORK SIZE

		Div_1	Div_small	Sliding window
Nodes		3.041	3001	2921
Edges	Unweighted	615.423	151.398	19.777
	Weighted	568.155	145.790	18.295

NODES IN MULTIPLE DISTINCT WORKS

		Div_1	Div_small	Sliding window
Nodes		715	713	713
Edges	Unweighted	164.565 (26.74%)	43.590 (28.79%)	8.610 (43.54%)
	Weighted	117.297 (20.65%)	37.982 (26.05%)	7.128 (38.96%)

JACCARD SIMILARITY – NODES PER WORK

Div_1

Div_small

Sliding window

COSINE SIMILARITY – NODES PER WORK

Div_1

Div_small

Sliding window

CENTRAL QUESTION

Can proximity be used to detect meaningful clustering as is done in other applications of SNA, such as ACA and CPA, in our corpus?

→ Remains open for future evaluation...

SLIDING WINDOW

Weighted edges

Fruchterman Reingold

Colour:

	Christian_mixed	(61,15%)
	Non_Christian_only	(26,37%)
	Christian_only	(12,48%)

Size: Degree

SLIDING WINDOW

Weighted edges

Fruchterman Reingold

Colour: Author

Size: Degree

FUTURE PLANS AND POTENTIAL

- Structurally record **attributes** and study the influence of attributes on the structure of the network
- Investigate whether shared patterns in mentions between authors relate to any part of the background of the author (ie. their education, their social group)
- Include mention context in study
 - Epithets, patronymics, ethnics etc.
 - Sentiment of context: positive vs. negative

THANK YOU!